

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 3.1 to AD4.1 – General Survey Questionnaire for Children (6 – 11 years)

WP 4

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¹ PU = Public

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CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

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Version 2	2023-07-12	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after external review of AD4.1
Version 3	2023-09-18	Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after GS partners' review of the questionnaires

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I.00: Questionnaire information

- Q093: Id (participant) _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q094: Id (interviewer) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q095: Date of the interview (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q095.1: Day _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q095.2: Month _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q095.3: Year _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q096: Start time (Priority.OPTIONAL)
 Q096.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)
 Q096.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)
Q097: End time (Priority.OPTIONAL)
 Q097.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)
 Q097.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)
Q098: Interview place / interview platform _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)

I.01: Personal information

- Q001: What sex was the child assigned at birth?
 Male
 Female
 Intersexual
(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q002: What is the child's birth date? (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q002.1: Year _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q002.2: Month _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q002.3: Day _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

I.02: Sociodemographic information

- Q003: In which country was the child born? _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q004: How long has the child been living...? Please indicate the number of years (or months if less than 1 year) and the child's current address(es). Please indicate all addresses if the child is in shared custody/parenting and the time spent in each address. (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.1: In this country (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.1.1: Years _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.1.2: Months _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.2: In your current address (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.2.1: Years _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.2.1: Months _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.4: Does your child live at more than one address?
 Yes
 No
(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q004.4.1: Address 1 details (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q004.4.1.1: Street name and number _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.1.2: Postal code _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.2: Address 2 details (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.2.1: Street name and number _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.2.2: Postal code _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005: What is the highest level of education attained by the parents/legal guardians? (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.3: Parent 1 or legal guardian (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.3.1: Level

No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)

Primary education (iscd 1)

Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)

Upper secondary education (iscd 3)

Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)

Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)

Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)

Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)

Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)

Other

Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.3.2: Specify other _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.3.3: Role

Mother

Father

Legal guardian

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.4: In case parents are divorced. New partner of the parent 1. (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.4.1: Level

No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)

Primary education (iscd 1)

Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)

Upper secondary education (iscd 3)

Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)

Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)

Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)

Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)

Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)

Other

Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.4.2: Specify other _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.5: Parent 2 or legal guardian (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.5.1: Level

No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)

Primary education (iscd 1)

Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)

Upper secondary education (iscd 3)

Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)

Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)

Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)

Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)

Other

Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.5.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.5.3: Role

Mother

Father

Legal guardian

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.6: In case parents are divorced. New partner of the parent 2. **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.6.1: Level

No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)

Primary education (iscd 1)

Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)

Upper secondary education (iscd 3)

Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)

Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)

Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)

Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)

Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)

Other

Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.6.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q007: What ethnic origin does the child have? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q007.1: Origin

Caucasian

Arab (including north africa and the middle east)

Sub-saharan african

Latin-american

South asian (including pakistan)

Far east asia (including china and the philippines)

Mixed/multiracial

Other

Do not know

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q007.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q008: Which language(s) is (are) spoken at home? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q008.1: National language(s) [country of study]

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q008.2: Another language

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q008.3: Specify language(s) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q100: Were the child's biological parents born in the same country as he/she? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q100.1: Mother

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q100.1.1: Please specify if in another country _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q100.2: Father

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q100.2.1: Please specify if in another country _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q101: What is the main labour status of the child's parents/legal guardians (if applicable)? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

I.03: Dietary habits

Q009: How often did the child consume the following food categories in the last 12 months? Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q009.1: Fish and seafood

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.2: Meat

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.3: Dairy products

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.5: Cereals

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.6: Fats (eg. Oil, butter, ...)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.7: Vegetables

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.8: Fruits

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.9: Snacks (e.G. Potato chips, bars, crackers...)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.10: Nuts

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010: How often did the child consume the following seafood and fish species items in the last 3 months? Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.1: White fish (e.G. Hake, snapper, sea bream, cod, haddock, grouper, halibut, tilapia, bass)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.1.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.1.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.2: Small oily fish (e.G. Anchovy, sardines, salmon) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.2.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.3: Big oily fish (e.G. Sword fish, tuna, school shark) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.3.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.4: Other sea food (e.G. Octopus, squid, shrimps, scampi) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.4.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.4.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.6: Sea bass - aquacultured **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.6.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.6.2: Portion

- A
- B

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.7: Sea bass **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.7.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.8: Swordfish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.8.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.8.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.9: Seabream **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.9.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.9.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.10: Tuna (excluding canned tuna) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.10.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.10.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.11: Tuna - canned **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.11.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.11.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.12: Mackerel (excluding canned mackerel) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.12.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.12.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.13: Mackerel - canned **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.13.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.13.2: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.14: Monkfish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.14.1: Frequency

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.14.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.15: Perch **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.15.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.15.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.16: Pike **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.16.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.16.2: Portion

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.17: Other fish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.17.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.17.2: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3/ week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.17.3: Portion

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.18: Other fish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.18.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.18.2: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.18.3: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.19: Other fish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.19.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q010.19.2: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3/ week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q010.19.3: Portion

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q011: Did the child eat fish or other seafood items in the last 14 days?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012: How often did the child consume the following food items in the last 12 months? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.1: Eggs **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.1.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.1.2: Portion sizes

A

B

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.2: Cabbages **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.2.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.2.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.3: Cucurbitaceae (cucumber, pumpkins, zucchini) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.3.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.3.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.4: Beans, peas and lentils **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.4.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.4.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.5: Orchard fruits (apples, pears, plums, figs...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.5.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.5.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.6: Strawberries **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.6.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.7: Other berries (grapes, blueberries...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.7.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.8: Dried fruits **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.8.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.8.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.9: Ready meals (in plastic packaging) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.9.1: Frequency

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.10: Fast food **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.10.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.11: Rice **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.11.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.11.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.12: Other cereals (barley, oats, bran, wheat, rye, maize) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.12.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.12.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.13: Mushrooms **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.13.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.13.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.14: Potatoes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.14.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.14.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.15: Leafy vegetables (e.G. Spinach, romaine lettuce, kale, swiss shard, endives, collard greens...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.15.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.15.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.16: Wild game meat **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.16.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.16.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.17: Offal **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q012.17.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.17.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.18: Processed meat (ham, sausage, bacon, deli meats (such as bologna, smoked turkey and salami), hot dogs, jerky, pepperoni) **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q012.18.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q012.18.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q012.19: Meat substitutes (eg: tofu) **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q012.19.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q012.19.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q013: In the past 12 months, how often were the eggs that the child ate from your own hens or received/bought from neighbours, friends, family or local growers?

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q015: How does the child usually eat vegetables and fruits? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q015.1: Vegetables

- Without skin
- With skin
- Both with skin and without skin

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q015.2: Fruits

- Without skin
- With skin
- Both with skin and without skin

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017: Did the child consume organic food in the last 12 months?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q017.1: How often did the child usually consume organic food in the last 12 months?

- <1 / month
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q017.2: Which percentage of the child's diet is based on organic food? Indicate a percentage for each of the following food items (0%= nothing organic and 100%= all the food consumed is organic) Choose from the following options: **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q017.2.1: Vegetables

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.2: Fruits

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.3: Bread

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.4: Meat

0% (never)

Less than 25% of the time

25% - 50% of the time

50% - 75% of the time

More than 75% of the time

100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.5: Eggs

0% (never)

Less than 25% of the time

25% - 50% of the time

50% - 75% of the time

More than 75% of the time

100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.6: Dairy products

0% (never)

Less than 25% of the time

25% - 50% of the time

50% - 75% of the time

More than 75% of the time

100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.7: Rice, pasta and other cereals

0% (never)

Less than 25% of the time

25% - 50% of the time

50% - 75% of the time

More than 75% of the time

100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.8: Other foods

0% (never)

Less than 25% of the time

25% - 50% of the time

50% - 75% of the time

More than 75% of the time

100% (always)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.8.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q018: Did the child eat vegetables and/or fruit from your own garden or received/bought from neighbours, friends, family or local growers in the last 12 months? If yes, indicate per season the portion you have eaten locally-grown

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

products (0%= nothing and 100%= all fruit/vegetables is from local sources) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q018.1: Fruits **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q018.1.1: Winter

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.1.2: Spring

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.1.3: Summer

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.1.4: Autumn

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2: Vegetables **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q018.2.1: Winter

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2.2: Spring

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2.3: Summer

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2.4: Autumn

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q019B: How much water does the child drink on average each day? (do also think of water in hot beverages and soups!)

- Less than 0,5 l/day
- 0,5-1 l/day
- 1-2 l/day
- 2-3 l/day
- More than 3 l/day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020: What is the main source of the child's water? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q020.1: Water for drinking

- Public network
- Bottled water (plastic)
- Bottled water (glass)
- Private well
- Others
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q020.2: Water for cooking

- Public network
- Bottled water (plastic)
- Bottled water (glass)
- Private well
- Others
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q020.2.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q020.3: Water for showering

- Public network
- Private well
- Others
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020.3.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q021: Do you use water purification devices or water filtering systems for the child's water? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q021.1: Water for drinking

- Filter (faucet attachment, refrigerator filter)
- Water softener
- Other
- No treatment
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q021.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q021.2: Water for cooking

- Filter (faucet attachment, refrigerator filter)
- Water softener
- Other
- No treatment
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q021.2.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q022: In which of the following bottling types does the child usually drink beverages? Please consider all beverages (fruit juices, ice tea, soft drinks...) including water (multiple answers possible) Choose from the following options:

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.1: Beverages in glass bottling

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q022.2: Beverages in plastic bottling

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.3: Beverages from decorated colored glass

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q022.4: Canned beverages

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.5: Drinks prepared in metal recipients (e.G. Arabic teapot)

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.6: Other types

- Yes
- No

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q022.6.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q022.7: Don't know

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q023: Do you use the following containers for keeping the child's food in the refrigerators or for longer-time storage elsewhere? If yes, how often do you use it? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q023.1: Hard plastic containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.2: Soft plastic container

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.3: Baking paper

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.4: Plastic bag

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.5: Aluminium containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.6: Ceramic containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.7: Glass containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.8: Others

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.8.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q024: Do you use the following containers for preparing or heating the child's food in the microwave oven? If yes, how often do you use it? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q024.1: Hard plastic containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.2: Soft plastic containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.3: Ceramic containers

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.4: Others

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.4.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026: Does the child consume dietary supplements (e.G. Vitamins and minerals)?

- Checked

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1: If yes, please indicate type, frequency and duration. **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.1: Vitamin a

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.1.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.1.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.1.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.2: Vitamin b/ b-complex

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.2.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.2.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.2.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.3: Vitamin c

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.3.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.3.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.3.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.4: Vitamin d

- No

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.4.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.4.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.4.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.5: Vitamin e

- No
 Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.5.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.5.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.5.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.6: Iron

- No
 Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.6.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.6.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.6.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.7: Zinc

- No
 Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.7.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.7.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.7.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.8: Selenium

- No
 Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.8.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.8.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.8.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.9: Calcium

- No
 Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.9.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.9.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

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Q026.1.9.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.10: Fish oil

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.10.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.10.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.10.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.11: Folic acid

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.11.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.11.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.11.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.12: Algae or seaweed supplement

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.12.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.12.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.12.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.13: Multivitamins supplement

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.13.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.13.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.13.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.14: Multiminerals supplement

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.14.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q026.1.14.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.14.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q026.1.15: Omega-3 fatty acid supplements

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q026.1.15.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.15.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.15.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.16: Other supplements

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.16.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q027: How often did the child eat dishes from communal catering, such as from a canteen, dining hall or cafeteria in the last 4 weeks?

(nearly) never

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

1 / day

2 or more / day

7 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q106: Did the child eat any of the following toddler foods in the last month (if yes, please specify the frequency)? Glass jars with metal lids: **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q106.1: Desserts

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1 / week

2-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q106.2: Fruits

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1 / week

2-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q106.3: Meats

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1 / week

2-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q106.4: Vegetables

(nearly) never

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- 1-3 / month
- 1 / week
- 2-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q107: In the last 4 weeks, did the child consume fast food and ready meals (prepared dishes as frozen pizza and the like) (please consider also beverages)?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1: If yes, how was it packed and how often did he/she consume it? Per type of pack:

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.1: In cardboard box

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.2: In paper

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.3: In paper cup

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.4: In plastic cup

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.5: In plastic (e.G. Bag, box)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week

- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.6: In polystyrene foam (e.G. Box)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.7: In aluminium containers

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

I.04: Lifestyle

Q029: In relation to smoking habits, how many people living in the child's house smoke or vape regularly (indoors)? Please provide a number.

_____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1: For each of them, please indicate the average number of cigarettes smoked and the average times of e-cigarettes used per day indoors **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1: Member no.1 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.2.1: Times /day

- Once
- 2-5 times
- 6-10 times
- More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.1.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2: Member no.2 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.2.1: Times /day

- Once
- 2-5 times
- 6-10 times

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.2.2.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3: Member no.3 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.1.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.2.1: Times /day

Once

2-5 times

6-10 times

More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.3.2.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4: Member no.4 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.1.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.2.1: Times /day

Once

2-5 times

6-10 times

More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.4.2.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q030: In general, how long, on a daily average, did the child usually spend in the following indoor places where people smoke? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q030.1: At home

Never

<1h/day

1-4h/day

>4h/day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q030.2: Elsewhere

Never

<1h/day

1-4h/day

>4h/day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q031: Do those who visit the child's house smoke indoors?

Never

Rarely (less than 1 / month)

Sometimes (less than 1 / week)

1 / week

2-3 / week

4-6 / week

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q032: How often does the child use the following cosmetic and hygiene products in the last month? For each product, please indicate if possible the commercial brand mostly used. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1: Hair products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.1: Spray, lacquer, gel/mousse **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.1.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.1.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.2: Shampoo **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.2.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.2.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.3: Conditioner **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.3.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.3.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.4: Moisturizer cream **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.4.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.4.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.5: Dye, colour rinse **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.5.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.5.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.6: Bleaching products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.6.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.6.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.7: Perming products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.7.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.7.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.8: Relaxer **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.8.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.8.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.9: Other products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.9.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.9.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q032.1.9.3: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2: Cosmetics (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.1: Foundation (powder, liquid) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.1.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.1.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.2: Make-up remover (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.2.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.2.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.3: Lipbalm (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.3.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.3.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.4: Lipstick (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.4.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.4.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.5: Blusher (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.5.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.5.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.6: Eye make-up (e.G.Mascare, eye shadow, eyeliner, mask, crayon) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.6.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.6.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.7: Nail polish **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.7.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.7.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.8: Nail polish remover **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.8.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.8.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.9: Traditional cosmetics (kohl, surma, kajal, tiro, etc.) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.9.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.9.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.10: Other products **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q032.2.10.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.10.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.10.3: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3: Bodycare **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.1: Perfume / eau de cologne **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.1.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.1.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.2: Body soap / shower gel **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.2.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.3: Hand lotion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.3.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.4: Face cream **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.4.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.4.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.5: Face mask **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.5.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.5.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.6: Sun cream (sunscreen) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.6.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.6.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.7: Sun tan lotion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.7.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.7.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.8: Anti-aging cream **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.8.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.8.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.10: Deodorant **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.10.1: Frequency

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.10.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.11: Shaving cream or aftershave lotion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.11.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.11.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.12: Body oil or body lotion (cream, milk, ...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.12.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.12.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.13: Skin bleaching products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.13.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.13.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.14: Mouthwash **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.14.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.14.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.15: Dental floss **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.15.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.15.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.16: Other products **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.16.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.3.16.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.16.3: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q033: Did you carry out any of the following activities with the child as diy (do-it-yourself) activities or hobbies and/or was the child exposed to any of these substances in these activities in the last 3 months? (please, do not count your professional activity) **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q033.13: Gardening products (fertilizers and pesticides)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q033.14: Sewage sludge (as fertilizer)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q033.17: Biocides (as fungicides or bactericides)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q036: Does the child have any artificial joints, pins, plates, metal suture material, or other types of metal objects in his/her body? (do not include piercings, crowns, dental braces or retainers, shrapnel, or bullets.)

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q037: How often does the child usually wear metallic jewelry or watch bracelet, excluding gold, silver or platinum jewelry/bracelet?

Never/rarely

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Sometimes (few times a month)

Always (almost daily)

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q038: Please, indicate how much time per day, on average, the child has used electronic devices such as mobile phones, computers, tablets, gps... In the last month? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1: Portable devices (mobiles, tablets, laptops, gps...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2: Desk devices (computer desk...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1: Portable devices (mobiles, tablets, laptops, gps...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2: Desk devices (computer desk...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q039: How long does the child dedicate to sport and/or physical activities? Please consider all the activities of the child (at school, after-school activities, hobbies etc.) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q039.1: Weekdays

No time

Less than 1 hour/day

1 hour/day (approx.)

2 hours/day (approx.)

3 hours/day (approx.)

4 hours/day (approx.)

> 4 hours/day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q039.2: Weekends

No time

Less than 1 hour/day

1 hour/day (approx.)

2 hours/day (approx.)

3 hours/day (approx.)

4 hours/day (approx.)

> 4 hours/day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040: Which of the following best describes the child's current physical exercise? Choose from the following options:

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.1: Light physical exercise for relaxation **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q040.1.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

- 1 / week
- A few times per week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.1.2: Duration

- 10-30 minutes
- >= 30 minutes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.2: Medium and intensive physical exercise **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q040.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1 / week
- A few times per week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.2.2: Duration

- 10-30 minutes
- >= 30 minutes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.3: Intensive (vigorous) physical exercise (sweating/out of breath) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q040.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1 / week
- A few times per week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.3.2: Duration

- 10-30 minutes
- >= 30 minutes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q041: How often (times per day) does the child wash his/her hands?

- Twice a day or less
- 3-6 times a day
- More than 6 times a day
- Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q042: Does the child have a habit of putting objects made of plastic (e.G. Pens, glasses or toys) in your mouth and chewing on them?

- No
- Yes

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q042.1: If yes, please specify the frequency

- Daily
- Several times per week
- Less often
- Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q043: Does the child regularly wear plastic or rubber shoes such as e.G. Flip-flops, beach shoes, swimming shoes, crocs

® or clogs without socks?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

I.05: Residential environment and home exposures

Q044: In which area is your home located?

City centre

Near city centre

Suburb/metropolitan area

Industrial

Rural/village

Other areas

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q044.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q046: Is the child's current home address and/or previous home address located near any of these facilities?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.1: Agricultural fields (including vineyards and orchards)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.2: Greenhouses

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.3: Natural spaces (parks, national parks...)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.4: Firefighting facility, military base, airfield

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.5: Landfills, dump sites, sewage sludge treatment

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.6: Waste incinerator, power plant based coal, oil, gas or wood

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.7: Other sites where pesticides are used (e.G., golf yards, railway...)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047: Is the child's current home address and/or previous home address located near any of these industries?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.1: Chemical industry (plastics, pesticides, tannery, pigments, cement, fertilizers,...)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.2: Paper or textile industry

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.3: Metal industry (metals, no-ferro, steel, metal smeltery)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.4: Electronics (computer, electronics, photovoltaic devices, solar cells)

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.5: A recycling plant, scrap yard, car repair plant

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.6: A glass factory

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.7: A site where medical equipment is produced

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.8: Other industrial facilities

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.8.1: Specify facility _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q048: Does your house have garden and/or vegetable garden?

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q048.1A: Has your garden been treated with pesticides in the last 12 months?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q048.1B: Has your vegetable garden been treated with pesticides in the last 12 months?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q050: Has your house (inside) or the child's school been treated with herbicides, fungicides and/or insecticides in the last 4 weeks? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q050.1: House

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q050.2: Child's school

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q052: In the last 12 months, were insecticide/pesticide products used to control or repel pest problems in your garden? (e.G. Snails/slugs, weeds, mosses/lichens, other garden pests/insects).

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q053: What is the main water source for your home garden irrigation?

Groundwater water (springs, wells)

Private well

Surface water (lake, river, streams, reservoir, ponds)

Rainwater

Others

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q053.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q054: Which of the following options best describes your home...?

Detached house

Semi-detached house

Townhouse

Flat/apartment

A farmhouse

Other (e.G. Caravan, mobile home)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q054.1: Flat/appartement: specify floor number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q054.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q055: What materials are used for most of the floor coverings in your home? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1: Non-textile flooring **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.1: Wood-parquet **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.2: Wooden planks **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.3: Laminate **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.4: Pvc **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.5: Linoleum **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.6: Tiles (e.G. Stone, marble, terrazzo) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.7: Other non-textile material **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.7.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q055.2: Textile flooring **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.1: Synthetic fibre [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.2: Natural fibre [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.3: Natural or synthetic fibre with plastic backing [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.4: Other textile material [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.4.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q056: Does the child help with general cleaning of your home? (general cleaning includes vacuum cleaning, mopping - use of cleaners/chemicals, disinfectant products in water, sweeping, dusting)

[] No

[] Yes, entirely

[] Yes, partially

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q056.1: In that case specify the percentage he/she is in charge of _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q057: If the child uses a vacuum cleaner for general cleaning of your home? Please, specify type and frequency of use

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q057.1: Type

[] Vacuum cleaner with air filter

[] Vacuum cleaner with water filter

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q057.2: Frequency

[] Less than 1 / week

[] 1 / week

[] 2 / week or more

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q160: Does the child clean the home with water? Please, specify the frequency.

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q160.1: Frequency

[] Less than 1 / week

[] 1 / week

[] 2 / week or more

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058: In the last month, were any of the cleaning products listed below used in your home, at least once a week? If yes, please specify if the cleaning product generally used is a classical or eco-friendly product (product featuring an eco-label on the package) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q058.1: Cleaning products (e.G. For kitchen, bathroom, floor, windows)

[] No

[] Don't know

[] Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.1.1: Type of product

[] Classical

[] Eco-friendly

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.2: Floor wax

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.2.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.3: Fabric softener

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.3.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.4: Wood varnish

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.4.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.5: Dry cleaning products (e.G. For cleaning upholstery, clothes, carpets)

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.5.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.6: Air freshener

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.6.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q058.7: Solvents (eg: cleaning solvents are acetone, toluene and trichloroethylene-tce. Common mild solvents include isopropyl alcohol, glycerin, and propylene glycol)

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.7.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.8: Spot remover products

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.8.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.9: Impregnation fluids (e.G. For upholstery, shoes)

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.9.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.10: Other cleaning products

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.10.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q058.10.2: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059: How much time on average does the child spend in the following places (referred to school days and weekends)?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1: Fall **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q059.1.1.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.3.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.3.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.1.3.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.4: In the family's car (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.4.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.4.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.1.4.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.5.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.5.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.1.5.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.6.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.6.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.1.6.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.7.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.1.7.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.1.7.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2: Weekends (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.1: Inside your home (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.1.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.1.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.2.1.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.2: Inside other houses (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.2.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.3.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.3.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.2.3.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.4: In the family's car (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.4.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.4.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.2.4.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.5.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.5.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.1.2.5.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.2.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1.2.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.2.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.1.2.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2: Winter **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.1.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.4: In the family's car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.1.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.1.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.1.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus

stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.1.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.1.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.1.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.1.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q059.2.2.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.4: In the family's car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.2.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.2.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3: Spring **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.1.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.4: In the family's car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.1.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.1.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.1.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q059.3.1.6.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.1.6.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.3.1.6.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.1.7.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.1.7.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.3.1.7.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2: Weekends (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.1: Inside your home (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.1.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.1.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.3.2.1.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.2: Inside other houses (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.3.2.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.3.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.3.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.3.2.3.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.4: In the family's car (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.4.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.4.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.3.2.4.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.5.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.5.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.3.2.5.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.6.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.6.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.3.2.6.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.7.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.2.7.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.3.2.7.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4: Summer (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1: Weekdays (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.1: Inside your home (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.1.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.1.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.1.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.2: Inside other houses (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q059.4.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.4: In the family's car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.1.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.2.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.2.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.2.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.4: In the family's car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.2.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.2.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

ANNEX 3.1 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q059.4.2.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.2.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q060: Did you have any of these situations at home? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q060.1: Breakage of a mercury thermometer

[] Yes

[] No

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.1.1: Timing

[] Less than 6 months ago

[] Between 6 and 12 months ago

[] More than a year

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.2: Breakage of an energy-saving lamp

[] Yes

[] No

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.2.1: Timing

[] Less than 6 months ago

[] Between 6 and 12months ago

[] More than a year

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.3: Which one(s) of these clean-up actions did you take? Please choose all that apply

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.3.1: Contained the spill by diking the mercury using rags

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.3.2: Picked up the pieces with rubber gloves on

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.3.3: Kept others away from the spill area to prevent the spread of contamination

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.3.4: Opened windows and doors in the area of the spill to provide ventilation during cleanup

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.3.5: Turned off heating, ventilating or air conditioning systems to prevent air circulation from the spill area to other parts of the house

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.3.6: Used a flashlight to determine if all the mercury was recovered

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Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.3.7: Other

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q060.3.7.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q061: Please complete the following information about redecorations and renovations made in your home.

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q061.1: Is your home currently being renovated? (major renovations: e.G. New walls, floor, windows...)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q061.2: Has your home been renovated in the last year? (major renovations: e.G. New walls, floor, windows...)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q061.3: Has your home been redecorated in the last year? (e.G. Painting, varnishing...)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062: How is your house usually ventilated? For each option, please specify frequency of use (months/year in which mechanical systems are used; hours/day for window ventilation by season) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q062.1: Mechanical ventilation system

No

Yes, always on

Yes, sometimes switched off

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.2: Ventilation through opening windows or doors

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.2.1: Frequency (autum-winter)

Nearly never

Less than daily

Daily – for a short time

Daily – for longer time (e.G. Half a day or whole day)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.2.2: Frequency (spring-summer)

Nearly never

Less than daily

Daily – for a short time

Daily – for longer time (e.G. Half a day or whole day)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

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Q062.3: Does your house have ventilation grilles in windows/doors or walls?

- No
- Yes, but they are sometimes closed
- Yes, they are always open
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q063: Do you have any pets at home or did you have any pets at home in the last 12 months? If so, specify type and number **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q063.1: No animal **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.2: Dog

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q063.2.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.3: Cat

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q063.3.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.4: Bird

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q063.4.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5: Other animal

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q063.5.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5.1.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5.2.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

I.07: Health status

Q073: How tall is the child (in cm)? _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q074: How much does the child weigh (in kg)? _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q078: Does the child use glasses and/or contact eye lenses?

- Yes, glasses
- Yes, contact lenses
- Yes, both
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079: Has the child or any of the child's biological family members (father, mother, grand-mother, grand-father, siblings...) been diagnosed by a medical doctor with any of the following diseases or conditions? If yes, has it occurred within the last 12 months? Please specify how old the child was when this was first diagnosed. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.1: Asthma (allergic asthma included) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.1.1: The child

- Never

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- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

- Q079.1.1.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.1.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.8: Rheumatoid arthritis (inflammation of the joints) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.8.1: The child
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.8.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.8.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.13: Type 1 diabetes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.13.1: The child
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.13.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.13.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.14: Type 2 diabetes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.14.1: The child
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.14.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.14.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.15: Thyroid disease **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.15.1: The child
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.15.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.15.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.16: Allergy (any other type than the following: allergic rhinitis, allergic conjunctivitis, allergic dermatitis) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 - Q079.1.16.1: The child
 - Never
 - Yes, in the past 12 months
 - Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.16.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

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Q079.1.16.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.17: Allergic rhinitis (nasal itching, sneezing, runny nose, or nasal blockage)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.17.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.17.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.17.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.18: Allergic conjunctivitis (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.18.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.18.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.18.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.19: Allergic dermatitis (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.19.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.19.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.19.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.20: Anaphylaxis (symptoms: airway constriction that makes it difficult to breath, shock with severe drop of blood pressure, rapid pulse, dizziness, or lightheadedness) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.20.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.20.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.20.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.22: cirrhosis or fibrosis of the liver/liver disease or dysfunction (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.22.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.22.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.22.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.23: kidney disease or dysfunction (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.23.1: The child

Never

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- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.23.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.23.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.24: cancer (malignant tumour, also including leukaemia and lymphoma) (see next question to specify kind of cancer) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.24.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.24.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.24.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.25: Severe headache such as migraine **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.25.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.25.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.25.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.27: chronic anxiety **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.27.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.27.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.27.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.28: Chronic depression **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.28.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.28.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.28.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.29: Other mental health problems **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.29.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.29.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

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Q079.1.29.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.31: attention deficit disorders (add, adhd) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.31.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.31.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.31.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.32: Autism or autism spectrum dysfunction (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.32.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.32.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.32.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.33: asperger syndrome (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.33.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.33.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.33.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.34: Down syndrome or other chromosomal disorder (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.34.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.34.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.34.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.36: Learning disability (dyslexia and etc.) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.36.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.36.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.36.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.37: Neurological disorders (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.37.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

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3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

- Q079.1.37.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.1.37.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.1.38: Permanent injury or defect caused by an accident **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.1.38.1: The child
[] Never
[] Yes, in the past 12 months
[] Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

- Q079.1.38.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.1.38.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.1.41: Other diseases or conditions. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.1.41.1: The child
[] Never
[] Yes, in the past 12 months
[] Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.41.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.1.41.1.2: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**
Q079.1.41.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.1.41.2.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2: If you answered “yes” for cancer, please specify what kind of cancer. Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.1: Bladder [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.2: Blood [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.3: Bone [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.4: Breast [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.5: Cervix(cervical) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.6: Colon [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.7: Esophagus (esophageal) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.8: Brain [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.9: Gallbladder [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.10: Kidney [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.11: Larynx/windpipe [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.12: Leukaemia [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.13: Liver [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.14: Lung [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.15: Lymphoma/hodgkin's disease [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.16: Melanoma [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.17: Mouth/tongue/lip [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.18: Nervous system [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.19: Ovary(ovarian) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.20: Pancreas(pancreatic) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.21: Prostate [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.22: Rectum (rectal) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.23: Skin(non-melanoma) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.24: Skin (don't know what kind) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
Q079.2.25: Soft tissue (muscle or fat) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

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Q079.2.26: Stomach [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.27: Testis (testicular) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.28: Thyroid [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.29: Uterus (uterine) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.30: Other [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.30.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.2.31: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.42: Puberty development problems or gynaecological diseases **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.42.1: The child

[] Never

[] Yes, in the past 12 months

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.42.1.2: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.42.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080: During the past two weeks, has the child used any medicines or homeopathic medicines?

[] Yes

[] No

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1: If yes, please indicate the commercial name(s) of the medicine, for which condition, the indication, as well as the strength of the drug, dose and frequency of use. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.1: Medicine 1 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.1.1: Commercial name _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.1.2: Condition _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.1.3: Indication _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.1.4: Dose _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.1.5: Frequency of use _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.2: Medicine 2 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.2.1: Commercial name _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.2.2: Condition _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.2.3: Indication _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.2.4: Dose _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.2.5: Frequency of use _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.2.6: Starting date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.2.7: Ending date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.3: Medicine 3 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.3.1: Commercial name _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.3.2: Condition _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.3.3: Indication _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.3.4: Dose _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.3.5: Frequency of use _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.3.6: Starting date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.3.7: Ending date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.4: Medicine 4 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.4.1: Commercial name _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.4.2: Condition _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.4.3: Indication _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080.2.1.4.4: Dose _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

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Q080.2.1.4.5: Frequency of use _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q081: Has the child started menstruating?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q081.1: What age did the child get her first period? Age at menarche _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q108: What is the child's head circumference? _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q109: What was the child's mother's age at his/her birth? _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q110: Did the mother of the child smoke while pregnant of him/her?

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q111: Had the child been breastfed when he/she was a baby?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q111.1: If yes, for how long had he/she been breastfed? Specify years or months, if less than one year

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q111.1.1: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q111.1.2: Months _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112: Does the child have or ever had dental sealant in his/her teeth?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.1.1: In how many teeth? _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.1.2: Don't know (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.2: When was the dental sealant placed last time? (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.2.1: Days _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.2.2: Months _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.2.3: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.2.4: Don't know (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.3: When was the dental sealant removed from his/her teeth last time? (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.3.1: Days _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.3.2: Months _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.3.3: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.3.4: Don't know (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q117: What was the child's gestational age at birth (in weeks)? The gestational age describes the time elapses between the first day of the mother's last menstrual cycle to the birth date. A normal pregnancy can range from 38 to 42 weeks. Infants born before 37 weeks are considered premature. (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q117.1: Gestational age _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q117.2: Don't know (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q117.3: Refuse (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q118: What was the child's weight at birth (in g) (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q118.1: Weight _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q118.2: Don't know (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

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Q118.3: Refuse [] (**Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE**)